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The future of universities in a digitalized world from a STEM students' perspective

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ABSTRACT

The fast emergence of digital developments during the 4th industrial revolution is accompanied by a strong demand for institutions of higher education to adapt the methods of teaching to the digital world. The purpose of this paper is to investigate the possibilities offered to universities by digitalization, whilst also discussing the potential problems digitalization creates, from the perspective of STEM students. This paper reflects how European STEM students see the future of universities in terms of teaching methods, the use of online content and professors' competencies.

This research is based on the outcomes gathered from European STEM students with different fields and levels of study. The students' opinion was collected through several sessions, with diverse facilitation formats, at BEST Symposia on Education (BSE), organised by the Board of European Students of Technology (BEST).

The analysis demonstrates that digitalization is not only considered an efficient way for diffusing information, but also renders the work of the student more flexible and increases collaboration possibilities among students. A lack of social interaction that could hold back the development of essential social skills has been identified as the principal potential drawback. This paper contributes to the existing knowledge by drawing conclusions based on the opinions of STEM students. Along with complementary work, it could lead the way towards defining practices that maximize the beneficial effects of digitalization on higher engineering education and minimize its downsides.

1 INTRODUCTION

The 4th industrial revolution is introducing overwhelming developments at a fast pace. Artificial Intelligence, Data Analytics, Internet of Things and Robotics are some of the key players in what is described to be one of the biggest revolutions humankind has ever experienced. The implications of such technological developments across several fields, merging barriers between the digital, physical and biological dimensions, influencing society, politics, economy and education [1].

In the process of adapting and preparing current and future generations to this rapidly changing world, education has to be used as a central tool [2]. Science, technology, engineering and mathematics education, frequently referred to as STEM education, is a particularly important area to take into consideration for that regard. It is fundamental to understand what is the crucial set of skills students of these particular fields need to develop in order to successfully face the future challenges. How can universities provide preparation for the emerging revolution, where a few years of technological breakthroughs can represent a complete alteration on the world we face today [3][4]?

In order to understand how to engage with the emerging challenges and needs, it is also important to understand what new opportunities are now available and how to take the most out of them. Digitalization has fundamentally altered information dynamics, as accessing and sharing information has never been so easy. With the increasingly larger number of accessible mobile devices, processing and data storage, distance no longer represents a barrier to knowledge. Universities need to take this into consideration, understanding how to effectively guide students into the changing scenario, while also understanding how they can adapt themselves and harness digitalization in a successful way [5][6][7].

This paper explores the visions of STEM students regarding this matter, through the analysis of reports produced by the Board of European Students of Technology (BEST). BEST is a non-political, non-governmental and non-profit voluntary student association, present in 97 universities, across 34 different countries. Striving to create opportunities for students to develop themselves and grow internationally minded, BEST offers a set of different events that are intended to bring universities, companies and students closer. One of these events is the BEST Symposium on Education (BSE) [8].

2 METHODOLOGY AND MATERIALS

The Educational Involvement Department of BEST aims to gather students' opinions regarding their experience with higher education in order to improve STEM education. With this in mind, BEST organizes BEST Symposia on Education – BSEs (formerly known as Events on Education – EoEs) where students have the opportunity to express their concerns and suggestions on several education-related topics. Each of these events welcomes more than 20 European STEM students from different universities, fields of studies and cultural backgrounds. This diversity ensures a more comprehensive picture of the current situation of engineering education in Europe according to students.

During the week-long events, professors and facilitators from BEST deliver sessions and workshops about different problems based on the theme of the given BSE. Several facilitation formats are used, such as brainstorming, world café, SWOT analysis or group discussion, in order to achieve the desired outcomes of the sessions and engage students to actively participate. Professors, education experts and industry representatives are also invited to deliver sessions or give an introductory presentation

on the given topic in order to increase the quality of the content and to bring diverse perspectives to the participants. The outcomes of these events are collected and presented in reports, which are later used for further research and disseminated toward higher education stakeholders.

This paper is based on three BSEs held in Lisbon, Krakow and Aalborg in 2018, which sessions tackled either directly or indirectly the matters of digitalization and online learning, hence providing valuable resources for the analysis of students' perspectives on the paper topic. At BSE Lisbon, 21 students from 17 universities discussed the skills needed in Industry 4.0 as one of the focus points of the six working days [9]. During BSE Krakow, 21 engineering students from 18 universities gathered for 7 working days to provide input on the topics "Internationalization of Education in Europe", "Online Learning" and "Future Universities" [10]. BSE Aalborg received input from 24 students from 19 universities on the topics of "Future of Project Based Learning" and "Continuous Learning and Valuable Working – Employability". This event hosted the session "How will digitalization shape the future (Global and Collaborative) university" facilitated by an Associate Professor of Aalborg University [11].

The data presented in the next sections is collected from participants with different methodology. The most common type was group discussion, where students were divided into four to six groups, either clustered randomly and equally or according to similar field of study. Besides, answers from open questions and on-site questionnaires were also analyzed.

3 ADAPTATIONS OF YOUNG GRADUATES TO DIGITALIZATION: SKILLS NEEDED IN INDUSTRY 4.0

Industry 4.0 is a name given to the current trend of automation and data exchange in manufacturing technologies. It is commonly referred to as the fourth industrial revolution. Along with the changes in the industry, education has to be adapted in order to fulfil the needs of the future market. At BSE Lisbon 2018, students' opinions on which skills are most needed in the Industry 4.0 were gathered, and it was compared to what they are learning in their current curricula [9].

Firstly, participants were asked what kind of skills they think they will need in Industry 4.0. They were not given specific options when answering. All of the 21 participants agreed that a good knowledge of the English language and operating systems, being able to write reports, as well as the efficient use of email are important skills to master. Moreover, all of them stated that mathematics, multidisciplinary and programming play an important role.

Students were asked if they have a possibility to gain hard skills, defined as abilities that are acquired and enhanced through practice relevant for Industry 4.0 in their curriculum. 85,7% of students gave a positive answer, 9,5% replied that they are not sure, and 4,8% argues that their university curriculum does not provide possibilities to gain hard skills which are relevant for Industry 4.0.

When asked if there is a sufficient amount of time dedicated to the acquisition of these skills in their curricula, 52% of them gave a positive answer. Results are shown in *Fig. 1*.

Fig. 1. Students' opinions on the currently allocated time for developing skills relevant for Industry 4.0 in their university curriculum

Finally, students were asked if they can acquire specific hard skills relevant for Industry 4.0, out of a given list, in their university curriculum and if not, how they acquire them instead. Results are given in *Fig. 2.* and *Fig. 3.*

Fig. 2. Hard skills relevant for Industry 4.0 which students can gain in their university curriculum

Fig. 3. Ways in which students gain or have gained hard skills relevant for Industry 4.0 outside of curricula

Results show that some students feel that university programs are not up to date with the current business needs and trends. Moreover, some state a lack of multidisciplinary and contact with companies. Therefore, students often resort to online courses or materials to complete their education and gain new skills. In this regard, students' opinion on the matter of adaptation of teaching methods to the universities' digitalization should be studied.

4 ADAPTATION OF TEACHING METHODS TO THE UNIVERSITIES' DIGITALIZATION

4.1 Flexibility of study programs

Most of the universities nowadays offer a specific study program for each speciality that usually doesn't change for years. At the same time, the world is changing rapidly. Specialists required today need to be not only good in their field of study, but also flexible enough to foresee and adapt to the innovations and current trends.

At BSE Krakow 2018 [10], students were asked the question "In your university, can you select subjects you want to pick up?". Most of the students gave a positive answer, though some of them mentioned that the own selection of subjects is possible only in Master's programs or particular universities. The next question was, "Does the university offer enough options to choose from?". Only 38,5% of students replied that they are satisfied with the provided options for classes while 61,5% would like to have a bigger variety. Some students pointed out that the variety of subjects to choose from might depend on a study program.

In the students' opinion, the main advantage of having a choice in subjects in curricula is an increase in the motivation in learning. The current situation can be improved with the influence of business in the academic field, experts' opinion on the matter can be addressed to encourage universities. Students suggested that the experts from companies can be involved in creating curricula and deliver courses that are relevant for the market needs, which leads to increasing the demand for university graduates, and directly makes the university itself more prestigious. Another solution is online

courses provided by academic and business experts [10]. This is also a point where digitalization can be very a significant benefit.

4.2 The development of online learning

Online classes are direct results of digitalization. Their accessibility made them popular all around the world. At the same time, online courses cannot replace traditional classes. At BSE Krakow 2018 [10], students were asked what key factors make an online course successful. The results of the survey are shown in *Fig. 4*. The students' replies are presented on the horizontal axis, the percentage of people who agreed with the idea is on the vertical axis.

Fig. 4. Students' answers on the key factors of successful online classes

In the students' opinion, the most important factors to make an online course successful are:

- possibility to ask questions, make comments, speak up
- video transcription
- ensure that all students have the same background
- good quality of the video

Along with the development of technologies, online classes will probably transform. In *Fig. 5*, the brainstorm on the idea of online learning transformation is shown. The students' ideas are presented on the vertical axis, the percentage of people who agreed with the idea is on the horizontal axis. The ideas that received the highest support are: the development of laboratories through virtual reality and a 3D holographic professor.

Fig. 5. Students' ideas on the online learning transformation

All participants agreed that online learning can be the future of learning if the balance between online tools and social interaction is established.

5 THE WAY DIGITALIZATION WILL INFLUENCE THE FUTURE OF UNIVERSITIES

Independently of the other two BSEs, the session held at BSE Aalborg 2018 [11] corroborates the rationale of the abovementioned new skills, flexible study programs and online classes since students stated these as a consequence of digitalization. Students were divided into six different groups, were asked three questions and were given time to discuss them.

The first question was “What opportunities do you see in further digitalization of education?”. Five out of the six groups mentioned that the possibility to create online content through digital means increases the flexibility of studying and renders access to information easier, not only for students of the university, but also others not studying at university. Furthermore, three groups explained that online education is cheaper than going to university, thereby giving access to high-quality material to a broader audience. Finally, half of the groups mentioned the possibility to adapt the lecture materials to each student and make it more interesting than traditional ex-cathedra lectures.

The second question was “What disadvantages do you see in the digitalization of education?” The main concern expressed by every group was the lack of socialization of students that follow all their courses through their computer. According to them, the students' dependence on their digital devices is likely to increase, which could have negative repercussions on health as well as their learning experience. Indeed, a student might not see the reason to be physically present at university if he can benefit from the same information online, thereby missing out on all the social interactions and group dynamics university has to offer. Four groups mentioned a large amount of time and resources needed to adapt and maintain the infrastructure for the new technologies. Some also warned about possible misuses and the possibility of hacking.

The final question posed to the students was “What actions should universities take to realise the opportunities while minimizing disadvantages and risks, and what roles do students have?”. All groups agreed that universities should keep in mind that

technology is an addition to the current state of higher education, but it should not be a goal itself. Therefore, students suggested mixing digital content and traditional ex-cathedra classes as a possible way of approaching teaching in universities in the future. Furthermore, the idea of a trial period was mentioned, in order to verify if the proposed changes are efficient and students react positively, by giving them the possibility to give feedback.

6 CONCLUSION

The fast pace of technological breakthroughs and their evolution, constantly require students to develop flexible skills that allow them to adapt to the new working methods. In the perspective of STEM students, curricula development has to be balanced between hard skills, required to understand and keep up with the fast development of technology, and soft skills that allow students to learn how to adapt to changing market needs and opportunities.

Students believe that universities need to incorporate digitalization into their educational system. However, concerns are raised regarding possible repercussions on the social aspects of the learning process. Universities are not only the place to learn hard skills, they also play an important role in the self-development path of an individual. Full digitalization can have a strong impact on social interaction, group dynamics, and soft skill development. To prevent this scenario, digitalization should be used as a tool to complement and facilitate education, instead of a complete substitute for traditional teaching methods.

Along with complementary work, this paper could lead the way towards defining practices that maximize the beneficial effects of digitalization on higher engineering education and minimize its downsides. In addition, future BSEs can be the platforms to further investigate the STEM students' point of view on the effects of digitalization, taking into consideration the results of this paper.

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